

How to Reference a Web Archive: An Approach for Ethical and Transparent Referencing

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WEBCHILD has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7 2007-2013) (Grant agreement No. 101170060)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20508122

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Archived webpages are an invaluable source for researchers, journalist, and everyone else who are interested in the history of the past few decades. However, they can include a variety of potentially compromising information or other types of information that might have been removed from the live web for a reason. Archived web material might be freely available and accessible through a public web archive such as the Internet Archive. But even if the material might be publicly available, we encourage users to think of these sources as archival records. Most physical archives are working with embargo periods of at least twenty years.¹ Publicly available web archives such as the Internet Archive apply no such limit. With this free and direct access to an archived collection the WEB CHILD project believes researchers bear the responsibility to respect the creators of the source material. To us this means working with the materials through a methodology inspired by feminist ethics of care.²

This whitepaper introduces a referencing standard that can be used to refer to material from a web archive. This standard can be used to reference a document without making the individual source directly available in the reference. The aim of this is to keep the possibility to follow the archival traces of the research but at the same time protect the producers of the source material from immediate exposure by providing a clickable link. This idea goes against the clickable links suggested in multiple academic referencing styles such as the Chicago Manual of Style and the APA referencing standard.³

The standard presented in this document understands archived web material as archived documents. Therefore, referencing archived web documents should follow existing practises of referencing documents in traditional archives. Adhering to a referencing style that resembles how documents in physical archives are cited has two clear advantages. First, by referencing archived webpages as other source material is commonly referenced it becomes easier for historians (and everybody else) to think of material from the archived web as source material. Secondly, referencing sources from the archived web as proposed in this standard protects the producers of the documents, by not providing links to individual sources directly in a footnote.

¹ Jaak Valge and Birgit Kibal, 'Restrictions on Access to Archives and Records in Europe: A History and the Current Situation', *Journal of the Society of Archivists* 28, no. 2 (2007): 193–214, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00379810701611951>.

² Katie Mackinnon, 'Critical Care for the Early Web: Ethical Digital Methods for Archived Youth Data', *Journal of Information, Communication & Ethics in Society* (Bingley) 20, no. 3 (2022): 353–54.

³ 'Source Citations: Examples: Citing Web Pages and Websites', in *The Chicago Manual of Style*, 18th edn, by The University of Chicago (2024), <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/book/ed18/part3/ch14/psec104.html>; American Psychological Association, 'Webpage on a Website References', <https://apastyle.apa.org>, accessed 6 May 2026, <https://apastyle.apa.org/style-grammar-guidelines/references/examples/webpage-website-references>.

Researchers working with the archived web as a historical source have started questioning how these sources can be included in historical narratives in an ethically sound manner. Katie MacKinnon has introduced the term “archive promenade” where producers of websites in an archive are invited to co-experience their archived websites as part of the research process.⁴ Another way of thinking about ethically sound practices of working with sources from the archived web can be found in Avery Dame-Griff’s work on transgender histories of the internet, where a strict choice has been made regarding how material from the archived web is referenced. In Dame-Griff’s work, references to the archived web are never directly included even though the material can be available at the Internet Archive.⁵

The standard proposed here follows the format: Archive, Time of collection, URL, PWID, Accessed. By providing these five pieces of information in a deconstructed manner it is still possible for readers of any given paper to follow the references to the archive while at the same time providing a buffer between readers and the producers of the archived material. The primary way of protecting producers of the source material is here seen as the absence of a direct URL to the archive. In an age of digital publishing, the direct link to an archived website provides a too easy access point to material that can be personal or maybe never thought of as part of institutional memory.

Time of collection is specified in the standard ISO-8601 format YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ. An example of the format in use could be 2026-05-26T15:09:00Z. The T character indicates the change from date to time in the string and the Z is the time zone indicator, where Z resembles the UTC time zone with a zero-hour offset.

The standard requires the Unique Resource Identifier (URI) and a persistent web identifier (PWID) as URIs can change over time, while PWID is a persistent identifier, made for ever lasting references. A PWID looks like this:

urn:pwid:archive.org:2025-02-25T03:39:32Z:part:https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild

A valid bibliographic reference contains five elements:

⁴ MacKinnon, ‘Critical Care for the Early Web: Ethical Digital Methods for Archived Youth Data’, 356–57.

⁵ Avery Dame-Griff, ‘Introduction: Laying the Foundations’, in *The Two Revolutions, A History of the Transgender Internet* (NYU Press, 2023), 22, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/jj.13944194.3>.

Element	Description
The name of the archiving institution.	Name of the archiving institution as the institution prefers it e.g. Internet Archive or Netarkivet
The time of collection.	The date and time the webpage was added to the web archive. Often called harvest date, crawl time or the like. This date-time entry must follow the international ISO-8601 standard: YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ
Unique Resource Identifier (URI) of the archived page.	The identifier used to identify the original resource when it was on the live web e.g., https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild
Persistent Web Identifier (PWID) to the archived resource.	A PWID for the archived resource. An example is given below, and more information can be found in the official namespace registration for the identifier. ⁶
Date of access.	The date you as a user accessed the resource in the web archive. This date entry must follow ISO-8601: YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ

In text citations should be shortened to contain the three elements: The name of the archiving institution, the time of collection, Unique Resource Identifier (URI) of the archived page.

A citation style language file for use with Zotero or other referencing tools has been developed. It can be found in this Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/20424593>.⁷

Example of a reference

If you want to reference an archived version of the WEB CHILD project description which was located at the URL <https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild> and has been archived at the Internet Archive on the 25th of February 2025 at 03:39:32. An overview of a bibliographic entry for this reference is shown below:

⁶ Eld Zierau, *URN Namespace Registration for Persistent Web Identifiers (PWID)*, 2022, urn:pwid:archive.org:2022-11-27T18:33:21Z:part:https://www.iana.org/assignments/urn-formal/pwid; Eld Zierau et al., 'Towards Transnational Research Data Management Practices for Web Archives: Challenges and Possibilities', in *The Routledge Companion to Transnational Web Archive Studies.*, 1st ed., by Susan Aasman et al., Routledge Companions to the Digital Humanities Series (Taylor & Francis Group, 2025).

⁷ Victor Harbo Johnston, *Chicago Manual of Style 18th Edition - with Archived Web (Notes and Bibliography)*, 28 May 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20424593>.

Example citation:

Internet Archive , 2025-02-25T03:39:32Z , <https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild> , urn:pwid:archive.org:2025-02-25T03:39:32Z:part:https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild , accessed 2026-05-08

References would look like this in practise:

In text reference (footnote or endnote):

Internet Archive, 2025-02-25T03:39:32Z, <https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild>

Bibliography:

Internet Archive, 2025-02-25T03:39:32Z, <https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild>,
urn:pwid:archive.org:2025-02-25T03:39:32Z:part:https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild,
accessed 2026-05-08

Bibliography entry required

Current academic style guides do not require websites to be listed in a paper or books bibliography. The Chicago Manual of Style writes “If a bibliography entry is needed, adapt the note form accordingly.”⁸ This style guide differs on this point. All references to archived websites are to be listed as part of the bibliography. Authors can choose to include archived websites in their overall bibliography or choose to keep a separate source material bibliography as often seen when historians are working with other types of archival material.

⁸ The University of Chicago, ‘Source Citations: Examples’, in *The Chicago Manual of Style*, 18th Edition (2024), <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/>.

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urn:pwid:archive.org:2022-11-27T18:33:21Z:part:<https://www.iana.org/assignments/urn-formal/pwid>.
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Sources

Internet Archive, 2025-02-25T03:39:32Z, <https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild>,
urn:pwid:archive.org:2025-02-25T03:39:32Z:part:<https://cas.au.dk/en/erc-webchild>,
accessed 08-05-2026

